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Dynamics of the Generation Planning Program (Planning Program) in Anticipating Juvenile Delinquency in Riau Province

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Abstract

This research is a study of social problems that occur in the community, especially at the youth level that occurs in various regions in Riau Province. The large number of teenagers who fall into negative behavior such as drug abuse, free sex which eventually becomes the reason for early marriage, to contracting infectious diseases such as HIV/AIDS. The problems that threaten young people will have an impact on the quality of youth as development actors and readiness to build a family. So that as an effort to respond to various problems related to youth, the government carried out various programs and activities which were distributed to related agencies according to the main tasks and functions that have been regulated in legislation. To support law number 52 of 2009, it is very necessary attention from government agencies to realize the achievement of improving the quality of youth through the Generation Planning Program. This research is qualitative in nature with data sources from literature studies and other supporting documents. This research will produce findings in the form of the role provided by the Generation Planning program in anticipating and preventing juvenile delinquency in Riau Province. In the research results, it will also be found factors that hinder the success of the Generation Planning Program, one of which is the low understanding and attitude of the community towards this program.

Keywords: Generation Planning, Youth Generation, Riau Province

1. Introduction

Riau Province has 12 administrative areas, Cities, and Regencies which have regional autonomy functions. Adolescence is a transitional period from childhood to adulthood. Adolescent life is a life that is very decisive for their future life. In 2021, the population of Riau Province according to the age group of 10-19 years is very large, around 1,162,863 people, the number of adolescents aged 15-19 reaches around 1,130,837 people, and the

number of adolescents aged 20-24 is around 1,139,586 people. (Projection Data, 2021). Seeing the very large number, adolescents as the next generation of the nation need to be prepared to become physically, mentally, mentally and spiritually healthy humans. We must utilize the demographic bonus as much as possible so that the momentum of the demographic bonus, which is only once in the life span of a nation or region, can really contribute positively to creating the welfare of a region. This can be achieved with one of the prerequisites that all people of productive age do not become a burden of development but become development capital, which is proven by the fact that they are all productive, creative, innovative and also not unemployed.

The ideals of an advanced Indonesia must of course be filled with generations that are smart, resilient, productive and also have character. Therefore, in order for the demographic bonus to be optimally utilized and the ideals towards a golden Indonesia in 2045 towards an advanced Indonesia can be achieved, one of the efforts that we must always increase is to build the younger generation, especially teenagers, so that they do not get caught up in things that are detrimental to themselves such as drug / drug abuse, free sex, HIV / AIDS to early marriage. We cannot deny that today many of our teenagers are involved in drug use, free sex, early marriage and HIV/AIDS. The long-term use of drugs will certainly lead to dependence on these illegal drugs and even the danger of death is ready to lurk in our teenagers who have over-dosed the abuse of these drugs. There are many examples of how many teenagers who are trapped in drug cases are then unable to continue their education to a higher level or even their lives end up behind bars, aka prison. Even for adolescents who are already addicted to these drugs, healing takes time and requires a lot of money, which is certainly a burden on development.

Based on the results of the 2020 population census, the total population in Pekanbaru City is 983,356 people consisting of 495,117 men and 488,239 women. A large population is of course a major capital for development if the population is of good quality, but if the population is not qualified a large population is a burden that can hinder the pace of development to create prosperity. Based on the projected population of Pekanbaru City, in 2021 it will enter a demographic bonus where the productive age population is more than the non-productive age population or in other words the population dependency rate in Pekanbaru City is below 50, which means 2 (two) productive age residents bear 1 (one) non-productive age population. In the yellow background pocketbook, the Education Office of Riau Province Basic Data on the Education Number of schools according to status for 2021, a total of 29 public schools at the SMA, SMK, and SLB levels. And a total of 113 private schools at the SMK, SMK, and SLB levels. Adolescence can be said to be a productive age where youth can later contribute more to the development of a country, bearing in mind that youth is the nation's next generation and agents of change, so they have a very important role in helping the process of achieving a nation's goals (Afriзал, Munaf, Y., Yogia, M.A., Suri, D.M., Prayuda, R., Amri, P. (2023)).

Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood. Adolescent life is a very decisive life for their future life. In 2021 the population of Riau Province according to the age group of 10-19 years is very large, around 1,162,863 people, the number of teenagers aged 15-19 reaches around 1,130,837 people, and the number of teenagers aged 20-24 is around 1,139,586 people. (Projection Data, 2021). Seeing the very large number, youth as the next generation of the nation need to be prepared to become healthy human beings physically, spiritually, mentally, and spiritually (Akbar D., Setiawan A., Prayuda R., Putra A., Aznor A. and Yudiatmaja W. E. 2020). Of course, we must make maximum use of the presence of this demographic bonus so that the momentum of the presence of a demographic bonus that only occurs once in the life span of a nation or region can truly contribute positively to creating the prosperity of a region. This can be achieved with one of the preconditions that all people of productive age are not a burden for development but instead become capital for development as evidenced by the fact that they are all residents who are productive, creative, innovative, and also not unemployed.

The ideals of an advanced Indonesia must of course be filled by generations who are intelligent, tenacious, productive, and also with character. For this reason, so that the demographic bonus can be used optimally and we can achieve the goal of achieving a golden Indonesia in 2045 towards an advanced Indonesia, one of the efforts that we must always improve is to build the younger generation, especially teenagers, so they don't get stuck in things that harm themselves such as drug abuse, free sex, HIV/AIDS to early marriage. We cannot deny that these days many of our youth fall into drug use, free sex, and early marriage and are exposed to HIV/AIDS.

Long-term use of drugs/drugs will certainly lead to dependence on these illegal drugs and even the danger of death is ready to lurk in our youth who have overdosed on the abuse of these illegal drugs. There have been many examples of how many teenagers who are trapped in drug cases are unable to continue their studies to a higher level or even end their lives behind bars, aka prison. Even so, for teenagers who are already addicted to drugs/drugs, healing takes time and requires a lot of money, this is of course a burden for development.

In addition to drug use, free sex also hurts the demographic bonus and efforts toward a golden Indonesia in the future. Apart from causing unwanted pregnancies or pregnancies outside of marriage, free sex among adolescents who often change partners can also lead to HIV/IDS. To this day, no cure has been found. Free sex that results in unwanted pregnancies in adolescents can also result in unsafe abortion decisions being carried out by adolescents, and of course, this will also increase the risk of maternal mortality and infant mortality due to unsafe abortions.

The incidence of early marriage among adolescents, especially girls under the age of 19 (nineteen) due to various causal factors, can also hurt the women themselves. Women who are married under the age of 19 (nineteen) years mean that their reproductive organs are not ready so when the woman has sex this can trigger what is called cervical cancer. Even so, if the woman is pregnant or pregnant, her child can have an impact on the incidence of stunting (Bentham, Jeremy. (2000)). This is because nutrition should only be intended for the fetus, but because the growth of the expectant mother is also not optimal, the nutrition consumed by the mother must be shared between the prospective child and the mother herself.

Table 1: Juvenile Delinquency in Riau Province by Regency/City in 2019-2021

No	Total Juvenile Delinquency Prov. Riau in 2019		Total Juvenile Delinquency Prov. Riau Year 2020		Total Juvenile Delinquency Prov. Riau in 2021	
1	Rohil	637,161	Rohil	647,791	Rohil	709,561
2	Rohul	561,385	Rohul	570,952	Rohul	692,237
3	Dumai	835,336	Dumai	923,452	Dumai	467,891
4	Kep. Meranti	206,116	Kep. Meranti	290,460	Kep. Meranti	490,501
5	Bengkalis	565,569	Bengkalis	573,504	Bengkalis	698,365
6	Siak	457,940	Siak	466,683	Siak	573,091
7	Pelelawan	390,046	Pelelawan	399,264	Pelelawan	495,167
8	Kampar	841,332	Kampar	857,752	Kampar	967,296
9	Pekanbaru	983,356	Pekanbaru	995,585	Pekanbaru	998,988
10	Kuansing	334,943	Kuansing	339,894	Kuansing	466,329
11	Inhil	654,909	Inhil	658,025	Inhil	792,561
12	Inhu	444,548	Inhu	453,241	Inhu	458,459
	Amount	6,498,661	Amount	6,889,603	Amount	7,309,885

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Riau Province

As seen in the table above there is an increase in juvenile delinquency every year and the city of Pekanbaru is the area with the highest rate of juvenile delinquency. Several youth problems that are counter-productive to optimal utilization of the demographic bonus and also our efforts towards Golden Indonesia to create a developed Indonesia must be overcome together (Canning, D., Finlay, JE, & Ozaltin, E. (2009). Efforts to prevent Indonesian youth in general and Pekanbaru City in particular from being trapped in early marriage behavior, risky behavior such as free sex, and also avoiding HIV/AIDS must be carried out together at home, at school, and in the community.

However, the condition of teenagers today is not without challenges. There are still problems that threaten youth, especially those related to reproductive health and nutrition which will impact their quality as development actors and their readiness to build a family (Davina, F. (2017). Puberty or earlier sexual maturity (internal aspect) and accessibility to various media and negative peer influences (external aspect) make adolescents vulnerable to risky sexual behavior. Thus, adolescents are vulnerable to experiencing pregnancies at an early age, pregnancies outside of marriage, unwanted pregnancies, and infection with sexually transmitted diseases to unsafe abortions. Currently, there are still 36 out of 1000 women aged 15-19 who have been pregnant and given birth. Compare with Australia 15 (2010), Algeria 9 (2008), and Andorra 4 (2010). In Indonesia, one in nine girls is married before the age of 18 (SUSENAS, 2016). Of the 62,558,408 families in Indonesia (the results of the June 2018 BDKI update), 2.66 percent of them are headed by males under the age of 19 (BKKBN, Profil Keluarga Indonesia, 2018).

Various studies have shown that adolescent girls aged 10-14 years have a five times higher risk of dying during pregnancy and childbirth than women aged 20-25 years. In addition, there is a risk of experiencing reproductive health problems such as cervical cancer and physical trauma to intimate organs. They are also 11 times more likely to be out of school (dropouts) compared to girls who are still in school. In terms of family resilience, have the potential to experience failure in building a family. BPS data (2010) shows that the highest number of divorce cases occurs in the age group of 20-24 years with less than five years of marriage. The high divorce rate in this group is a result of marriages being carried out at a young age so that they are not ready to live a family life. Women who are pregnant and give birth at an early age also have a high tendency to give birth to stunted children. The results of a study in 55 middle- and low-income countries show that there is a relationship between the age of the mother at childbirth and the incidence of stunting: the younger the mother at the time of delivery, the more likely she is to give birth to a child who is stunted (Herdiana, E. (2022). BPS data (2010) shows that the highest number of divorce cases occurs in the age group of 20-24 years with less than five years of marriage.

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The Planning Program program is a government strategy to address human development issues, especially adolescents. This program focuses on fostering Indonesian adolescents to become visionary adolescents who avoid the risk of the KRR Triad (Sexuality, HIV / AIDS, Drugs). The conclusion of this research is that this program has two approaches, namely Bina Keluarga Remaja (BKR) and Information Counseling Center (PIK). The program is implemented with several strategies including: approach, youth friendly, learning, institutionalization, and achievement. The suggestion given for this research is that BKKBN Bandar Lampung City should make a clearer SOP for implementing the program when making program planning, increase socialization with related institutions to develop this program because not all teenagers know its existence, and hold a periodic evaluation activity to measure the success of achieving its targets. One of the efforts made to address these youth problems is through the Generation Planning Program (Planning Program) through the Youth Information and Counseling Center (PIKR), Youth Family Development (BKR), Riau Indonesian Planning Program (GIR), and Planning Program Forums in every District/District. City (Maulana, JF (2020).

The Planning Program program is a program that promotes the formation of national character among the younger generation. The Planning Program program is a forum for developing national character because it teaches youth to stay away from Early Marriage, Premarital Sex, and Drugs to become resilient youth and be able to contribute to development. PLANNING PROGRAM (GENeration planning) is a program developed by the National Population and Family Planning Agency (BKKBN) with program target groups, namely: Teenagers aged 10-24 years but not married, Unmarried students/students, Families, Communities who care about the lives of teenagers The purpose of developing the Planning Program program by BKKBN is to prepare family life for adolescents in terms of Planned educational levels, Careers in planned jobs, and Marriage with full planning by the reproductive health cycle.

Since the beginning of 2013, the promotion of the Generation Planning Program has been encouraged through advocacy programs aimed at forming youth family development forums and youth or student information and counseling centers. According to data from the Women's Empowerment Service, Child Protection and Population Control in Riau Province. In Pekanbaru City in 2021 there will be 34 Youth Family Development groups and 13 Youth Information and Counseling Center groups and 1 Student Information and Counseling Center group that has been formed. The establishment of Information and Counseling Centers for Youth or Students was achieved at almost all levels of the region starting from sub-districts to village areas, both education pathways (SLTP basis, SLTA base, AND SLTA base and PT base) as well as social pathways based on religion, youth, and others. In overcoming the youth problem, the Indonesian government, through the BKKBN, has a Generation Planning Program, one of the targets of which is youth. For this reason, this research will focus on "Dynamics of Planning Program Programs in Efforts to Prevent Juvenile Delinquency in Pekanbaru City, especially those related to early marriage, free sex, drug/drug abuse, and also HIV/AIDS".

2. Research Method

The method chosen in conducting research is descriptive qualitative. Where the author emphasizes the analysis of literature. Qualitative methods are more adaptable to many shared influences and the pattern of values encountered. By using a qualitative research approach, researchers can recognize subjects and feel what they experience in everyday life. Qualitative research emphasizes the ongoing process that occurs rather than focusing on results. This study uses data collection techniques in the form of literature studies. The data from this study were selected and processed from various literature such as scientific journals, books, magazines, newspapers, and visits to internet websites and other sources that support research.

Qualitative research methods are often called naturalistic research methods. The research is carried out in natural conditions (natural setting), also known as the ethnographic method because initially this method was used more for research in the field of cultural anthropology, referred to as a qualitative method. After all, the data collected is analyzed. more qualitative (Sugiyono, D. 2001).

3. Results and Discussion

Good and quality service has implications for community satisfaction which is a benchmark for the success of government administration. The Planning Generation program was socialized to various schools and universities as a response to Law No. 52 of 2009 on Population Development and Family Development. Article 48 paragraph 1 (b) of the Act states "Improving the quality of adolescents by providing access to information, education, counseling and services on family life". The Generasi Berencana (Planning Program) program is seen as suitable for the current conditions, namely problems surrounding adolescent issues such as sexuality, HIV AIDS, low knowledge of reproductive health, and the relatively low average age of first marriage for women. The Planning Program program is a program to facilitate the realization of Tegar Remaja, namely adolescents who behave healthily, avoid the risk of the KRR Triad, delay the age of marriage, have family life planning to create a Small Happy Prosperous Family and become examples, models, idols and sources of information for their peers. Planning Program are teenagers/students who have the knowledge, attitude and behavior as teenagers/students, to prepare and plan carefully for family life. Planning Program teenagers or students who are able to go through the levels of education in a planned manner, have a career in a planned job, and get married with full planning according to the Reproductive Health cycle.

Efforts made to overcome the problems of adolescents, including through the Youth Reproductive Health Information and Counseling Center (PIK KRR) will be very meaningful to answer the problems of adolescent reproductive health. In addition, it is also a means for adolescents to consult to develop their positive willingness and ability. Youth Counseling Information Center (PIK Remaja) is a forum for activities of the Family Life Preparation program for adolescents managed from, by and for adolescents to provide information and counseling services on reproductive health and family life planning.

Future planning for teenagers is an important thing that needs to be prepared as much as possible. Generally, teenagers have not considered that there is no need to think about it when they are still in education. Although everyone has different talents and interests, still, there are many teenagers who carelessly follow their peers and make the wrong decision in taking their field of study. The Indonesian government through the generation plan (Planning Program) program seeks to direct adolescents regarding their future. The purpose of this study is to describe adolescents' preferences in the generation plan (Planning Program) program in terms of adolescents' characteristics and their access to information in Padang city. Therefore, this paper hopes that the generation plan (Planning Program) socialization program needs to be improved and further socialized through social media for further development.

The implementation of the Generation Planning Program in preparing family life for adolescents by the Sumenep District Office of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Family Planning has not been successfully implemented to the maximum where it can be seen from the increasing number of early marriages in Sumenep District. Communication in the aspect of socialization has been done well but in the aspect of communication intensity has not been done optimally. Resources which include Human Resources (HR) implementing the Generasi Berencana Program are disproportionate to the coverage of the program's target area, while facilities and financial resources are sufficient to support the implementation process of the Generasi Berencana Program. The disposition of employees of the Sumenep District Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Family Planning Office is quite good and the operational procedures used by implementers are very easy to understand.

The goal of the Generation Planning Program related to reproductive health is to change behavior (behavior change). Health behavior change as the goal of health promotion or education has at least 3 dimensions, namely changing negative (unhealthy) behavior into positive behavior (in accordance with health values), developing positive behavior (formation or development of healthy behavior), maintaining positive behavior or behavior that is in accordance with health norms/values (healthy behavior by maintaining existing healthy behavior). The Generation Planning Program has been directed to be carried out throughout Indonesia, with the National Population and Family Planning Agency is the driving force and cooperates with the SKPD-BN in each region

which is the main actor in implementing this program. Based on data obtained from the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia at the Regional Office of Riau Province regarding "Recapitulation of Underage Marriage Data for Riau Province in 2019-2021":

Table 2: Data Summary of Underage Marriages throughout Riau Province in 2019-2021

No	Kab./Kota	Nikah Di Bawah Umur <19 Th								
		Tahun 2019			Tahun 2020			Tahun 2021		
		Pria	Wanita	Total	Pria	Wanita	Total	Pria	Wanita	Total
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	Indragiri Hulu	31	213	244	6	95	101	35	99	134
2	Indragiri Hilir	0	0	0	15	21	36	15	173	188
3	Bengkalis	10	10	20	8	28	36	16	49	65
4	Siak	63	98	161	14	44	58	19	26	45
5	Kampar	64	318	382	22	45	67	7	23	30
6	Pekanbaru	21	113	134	4	35	39	13	27	40
7	Rokan Hulu	8	235	243	46	131	177	40	183	223
8	Rokan Hilir	46	211	257	62	167	229	23	74	97
9	Pelalawan	30	137	167	5	24	29	11	34	45
10	Kuantan Singingi	24	129	153	6	41	47	13	53	66
11	Dumai	36	17	53	2	16	18	1	8	9
12	Kepulauan Meranti	13	52	65	12	51	63	29	59	88
JUMLAH		346	1.533	1.879	202	698	900	222	808	1.030

It can be seen from the table above that the number of underage marriages in the province of Riau is very large. Several factors influence the occurrence of this, namely because these teenagers come from Broken Home families, lack of communication between children and parents, children receive less supervision, and children are trapped into promiscuity. Based on the Generation Planning program manual, eight functions of the family greatly influence the mindset of children (adolescents) that can keep them away from activities that lead to juvenile delinquency. The eight family functions are environmental function, economic function, socialization and education function, reproductive function, protection function, love function, socio-cultural function, and religious function. One of the efforts made by the Planning Program program to combat the rate of early marriage is to describe one of the programs, namely by providing information or conducting outreach to prevent early marriage and improve counseling services.

The Planning Program program is implemented using two approaches, namely the approach to the youth themselves and the approach to families who have adolescents. Where the approach to adolescents is carried out through the development of a Youth Counseling Information Center/Student Center (PIK R/M) which is carried out through approaches from adolescents, by adolescents, and for adolescents. Through this program, adolescents will be provided with information about the importance of reproductive health, life skills, and skills, and counseling services to realize the youth tag in achieving a happy, prosperous small family (Prayuda, R., Syafrinaldi, Akbar, D, Nurman, Sary, D.V. (2022). There are as many as 58 PIK R/M in Pekanbaru for Information and Counseling Centers for Youth/Students where each village has one PIK R/M and the BKKBN also distributes them to every school and tertiary institution.

Based on the data in the table above, it can be seen that the effectiveness of the Planning Program Program in preventing juvenile delinquency in Riau Province is still minimal or has not been implemented properly, this is because the growth in the number of delinquents that occur among adolescents continues to increase every year in Riau Province. The Planning Program program is also still experiencing problems with its program target, namely youth, this is due to the lack of outreach to youth followed by a low level of youth participation in this

program. This low participation was due to the youth who were invited to attend activities carried out by the Planning Program program choosing not to come.

The Planning Program program is able to become a good forum for adolescent character building, especially in strengthening civic responsibility. This success can certainly be achieved on various factors. One of the influencing factors is related to strategy. Some of the strategies needed are (1) Maximizing human resources by managing Planning Program program services; (2) Forming and developing PIK R in several regions; (3) Developing the Planning Program program; (4) Increasing Planning Program program partnerships; (5) Developing regular coaching and evaluation. Thus, the Planning Program Program is able to produce adolescents who can be educated consistently and in accordance with their capacity through increasing their potential while forming civic responsibility.

The substance of the Generation Planning Program contains various things aimed at solving and anticipating the problem of juvenile delinquency. However, the policy direction embodied in the implementation of activities is not appropriate and includes things to prevent and overcome problems that occur, this policy direction is not very effective because the policy direction is more focused on prevention but not yet on policy directions that deal with problems (Pyas, DW, & Satlita, L. (2017).

Based on the target that the Generation Planning program focused on, namely youth aged 10 to 24 years and not married, although this target was what had been planned, this target was not optimal because the target (youth) was not ready for intervention where there were still many young people who consider that some of the points carried out in the Generation Planning program are inappropriate or taboo to discuss with others, for example, such as discussing their Reproductive Health. So the readiness of the public to participate in the activities carried out by the Generation Planning Program is not fully ready.

In the aspect of accuracy in the process of carrying out the Generation Planning program in Riau Province, its implementation has also not been effective, this can be seen from the fact that most of the general public does not understand correctly or even do not know all about the substance of the Generation Planning (Planning Program) program that is being attempted so that they also do not know what the benefits of this program. Several inhibiting factors hinder the success of the Generation Planning (Planning Program) program, namely the existence of moral deviations that occur among adolescents, this occurs due to a moral crisis which is an accumulation of lack of attention from parents, bad associations, and the surrounding environment. Therefore all adolescent problems cannot be separated from the role of parents to be able to control their children in carrying out their daily activities. Then the obstacles that occur are in the form of norms in society that become disguised so that culture and norms are increasingly eroded. Such as the style of dress of European or Western society which is contrary to the norms of decency and customs in an area. The next obstacle was the lack of time given by the management of the Youth/Student Information and Counseling Center (PIK R/M) for the continuity of the Planning Program program. The administrators of PIK R/M are teenagers whose age limit is 24 years where they are part of school students or students who of course have agendas and schedules and activities that occur are of course different from one another. (HR) in terms of time and skills in the R/M PIK program. Finally, it has an impact on the lack of success of the planned generation program in the Riau Province area.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion above regarding the implementation of the Generation Planning program in Riau Province, it can be concluded that the implementation of the Generation Planning Program (GenRe) carried out in Riau Province is still not effective. And this does not happen solely because the administrators and the program are not being implemented as they should, but some obstacles come from the program's targets, namely young people who have minimal participation and are not interested in the program being launched. The success of the Generation Planning program certainly requires both parties to contribute and be active in the continuity of the GenRe program activities.

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